

JUSTNORTH: Conceptualizing Justice for a Sustainable Arctic

Forms of justice:

Substantive – the essence of justice

Procedural – procedure and representation

Distributive – allocation and distribution

Retributive – punishment, reparation and rectification

Recognition – who is heard and listened to?

The extensive literature on justice offers different ways of structuring, examining and assessing justice and injustice. This helps us understand both the concept of justice as well as justice in action. By asking what *forms of justice* are at stake in a particular economic activity or political process, we are able to better understand the potential application of justice concepts within that specific activity. In addition, by thinking about the *realms of justice*, these could be helpful to begin thinking through processes and relationships of justice and injustice. We suggest a way of categorizing and approaching an issue of justice and injustice, by asking how the five different *aspects of justice* affect the people, problems and processes in each development initiative.

Aspects of justice:

The subject of justice – **who** is, and who is not affected?

The object of justice – **what** is, and what is not at stake?

The domain of justice – **where** are the implications taking place, and where not?

The social circumstances of justice – **when** are injustices experienced, and when not?

The principles of justice – **which** are the relevant governing norms, and which are not?

How could these aspects be explained and assessed?

How can justice theories help us understand Arctic development?

Even if future economic development in the Arctic accords with one or several of the UN Sustainable Development goals, it will be unsustainable if it is not accomplished in ways that are – and are perceived from within different communities to be – ethically defensible and just.

Several distinct theories of justice already exist that help us understand justice and injustice in different ways and using different approaches. By reviewing existing scholarship on justice, a group of scholars in JUSTNORTH have identified some of the most prominent approaches to theorising justice.

These approaches are first divided into a set of schools of justice, covering the key arguments and critiques of Liberalism, Cosmopolitanism, the Capabilities Approach, Libertarianism, Feminism as well as different approaches of Radical theories of justice. The second set focuses on more applied approaches to theorising justice. Here we shift our gaze towards environmental justice and environmental ethics, climate justice, spatial justice, landscape justice and energy justice. Aspects such as intergenerational justice, indigenous approaches to justice and just transitions are also discussed. Visit our website for more information: www.justnorth.eu.

Iqaluit Utilidor (Photo: SM 2021)

Realms of justice:

- *Temporality* – what sort of past, present, and future time frames are relevant for a specific development initiative or economic activity in the Arctic?
- *Scale/scope* – what geographical extents and/or institutional levels are relevant in the specific context under scrutiny?
- *Locus of concern* – what kind of ‘place’ is relevant? Moreover, how could that concept be understood in a specific economic activity?
- *Source of harm* – what are the relevant forces that produce conditions of injustice in a specific development initiative or economic activity? Who is being exposed, and who is not?

Iqaluit Sunset (Photo: SM 2021)

Or visit our Website: WWW.JUSTNORTH.EU

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